

Trends in Research on the Use of Artificial Intelligence Applications in Turkish Language Teaching

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Abstract

Rapid technological developments in the twenty-first century have accelerated the integration of artificial intelligence into teaching and learning processes. This study examines articles and postgraduate theses on artificial intelligence and Turkish language teaching published between 2020 and 2025. The studies were analyzed according to publication year, type, department, research method, research design, data collection tools, data analysis methods, and AI technologies used. Document analysis, a qualitative research method, was employed. Publications indexed in the YÖK National Thesis Center, Google Scholar, and DergiPark were reviewed. Inclusion criteria required studies to be published between 2020 and 2025, written in Turkish, available in full text, and related to keywords such as Turkish language teaching, artificial intelligence, reading, writing, listening, speaking, and generative AI. Studies published before 2020, written in other languages, presented as conference papers, unavailable in full text, or published as books or book chapters were excluded. A total of 30 studies, including 20 articles and 10 theses, were analyzed through content analysis. Findings indicate that publication output increased significantly in 2024–2025, with articles constituting the majority of studies. Qualitative methods and literature review designs were predominant, while document analysis and semi-structured interviews were the most frequently used data collection tools. ChatGPT emerged as the most commonly examined AI application. The results reveal a need for more experimental and practice-oriented research and suggest that integrating visual and auditory AI tools alongside text-based applications may further enrich Turkish language teaching.

Keywords: Turkish language teaching; mother tongue education; document analysis; artificial intelligence applications.

Introduction

The first quarter of the twenty-first century stands out as a period marked by remarkable developments in the field of technology. The accelerating digital advancements of this era have directly impacted educational systems, making it imperative to adopt a technology-based approach to learning and teaching (Durmaz et al., 2024; Ünsal, 2024). Accordingly, the function of education has expanded beyond transmitting knowledge to encompass the development of competencies suited to the demands of the age, such as problem-solving, critical thinking, collaboration, and digital literacy (Cansoy, 2018). In order for this function to be fulfilled effectively, restructuring educational environments in alignment with technological developments has become unavoidable. The technological transformations occurring in this direction have offered opportunities to diversify pathways to knowledge, digitize materials, and beyond that, to make the instructional process more individualized, accessible, and flexible (Durmaz et al., 2024). Consequently, integrating advanced technologies into educational settings has ceased to be a pedagogical alternative and has become a necessity for students to adapt to changing and evolving conditions.

Literature Review

Artificial Intelligence and Education

Artificial intelligence applications stand at the center of this necessity and are among the technologies that most powerfully represent the transformation in education and instruction. Coppin (2004) defines intelligence as the ability to cope with new situations, solve problems, answer questions, and make plans, while defining artificial intelligence as a system that solves complex problems using methods based on intelligent human behavior. In parallel with this definition, Nabiyeu (2016) and Kayabaş (2010) emphasize that artificial intelligence is a field of technology capable of imitating cognitive processes inherent to humans, such as perception, reasoning, learning, and problem-solving. Machine learning, one of the fundamental subfields of artificial intelligence, enables computers to extract patterns from past data and make predictions and inferences without human assistance (Shinde & Shah, 2018). Underlying this process are deep learning algorithms that model the functioning of neurons in the human brain and analyze large datasets with high accuracy (Dargan et al., 2020). Natural language processing, which represents the point where this technological infrastructure meets human communication, is a significant communication-oriented subfield that enables the computational analysis of human language and allows texts to be understood and generated (Chowdhary, 2020). Generative artificial intelligence, which emerges from the integration of all these technologies, is capable of producing entirely new outputs such as text, visuals, or audio, and powerfully supports educational processes by responding instantly to the individual needs of students (Holmes et al., 2023).

Artificial Intelligence in Language Education

The most evident reflection of this support manifests itself in the transformation that artificial intelligence has brought about in the field of language education. Applications of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Generative AI (GenAI) technologies in language education constitute the fundamental dynamics of this transformation. Large language models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT and chatbot tools have been shown to offer considerable opportunities for developing students' core language skills (Son et al., 2023). These applications provide students with interactive learning environments where they can experiment without fear of making mistakes; they deliver instant feedback on topics such as text production and grammar through Automated Writing Evaluation (AWE) technologies (Albedah, 2025), and make language development more accessible by analyzing students' speech through Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) technologies (Son et al., 2023). Artificial intelligence assumes a supportive role in writing skill development through feedback, text generation, and text editing processes (Atasoy, 2025; Gün & Durmuş Öz, 2024), facilitates speaking practice by reducing student anxiety through chatbot tools (Afşin, 2025), and supports fluent reading development through its contributions to summarizing, question generation, and comprehension processes in reading skill development (Okkalı, 2025). With these features, AI-assisted applications serve as an assistant to teachers in language education, contributing across many areas from material design to assessment and evaluation (Gutiérrez, 2023).

Artificial Intelligence in Turkish Language Teaching

With the technological developments of recent years, interest in artificial intelligence applications in Turkish language teaching has also increased noticeably. AI tools used in the teaching of Turkish both as a native language and as a foreign language have laid the groundwork for new approaches to the development of language skills (Şen, 2023). A significant portion of the studies conducted in this field focuses on determining the AI awareness, attitudes, anxieties, and literacy levels of Turkish language teachers and pre-service teachers (Banaz, 2024; Banaz & Demirel, 2024; İçöz & İçöz, 2024). The findings reveal that this group views AI applications as a supportive tool in the educational process and generally demonstrates a positive approach toward these technologies (Aydoğdu, 2025; Sevinç & Yılmaz Özelçi, 2025).

Research focusing on the effects of AI applications on core language skills indicates that these technologies make significant contributions to the development of writing, creative thinking, and critical thinking skills in particular (Dal, 2024; Köçeri & Kırkkılıç, 2024). In the context of speaking skills, students' self-efficacy perceptions have been found to be positively influenced (Afşin, 2025). However, evidence also suggests that these effects do not translate equally across all language skills; for instance, while AI applications increase reading motivation, they do not produce a significant difference in reading comprehension compared to traditional methods (Ürkmez, 2025).

On the other hand, Turkish language teachers are reported to use AI applications primarily in content production, material development, and assessment and evaluation processes, while expressing various concerns regarding data privacy, plagiarism, ethical issues, and the potential weakening of students' critical thinking skills (Aydoğdu, 2025; Karagöl & Yıldırım Bilgen, 2025; Şimşek, 2025). Furthermore, it is emphasized that the AI literacy levels of teachers and pre-service teachers are influenced by variables such as gender, age, and technology use habits, and that systematic training in AI literacy is needed in undergraduate programs (Banaz & Demirel, 2024; Erol, 2024). It is also noted that, despite producing technically and operationally successful results, artificial intelligence has yet to reach the depth of the human mind and cognitive flexibility, and therefore carries certain limitations in the context of the relationship between language and intelligence (Kaya, 2023).

Research Gaps and Purpose of the Study

When the studies on the use of AI-assisted applications in Turkish language teaching are evaluated as a whole, it is noteworthy that the research is largely limited to situation assessment, opinion surveys, and literature reviews, and that experimental studies demonstrating the concrete effects of AI-assisted applications on learning outcomes remain quite scarce (Karagöl & Yıldırım Bilgen, 2025; Koparan & Şimşek, 2025). It is stated that AI applications for the evaluation of open-ended student responses in text processing constitute a significant gap at the national level (Aksoğan, 2025). In addition, there is a continued need for studies examining the effectiveness of AI-based materials developed within the scope of the Türkiye Yüzyılı Maarif Modeli [Turkey's Century Education Model] (Kır, 2025), for the development of instruments to measure secondary school students' attitudes toward AI (Öztan, 2024), and for research addressing the digital writing and AI literacy of pre-service Turkish language teachers (Erol, 2024). In this regard, these gaps in the literature necessitate the systematic examination of existing studies and a comprehensive evaluation of trends from a holistic perspective.

In line with this need, the purpose of the study is to examine articles and postgraduate theses on artificial intelligence and Turkish language teaching published between 2020 and 2025 according to predetermined criteria. Within the scope of this general purpose, the studies identified were classified and described according to the following criteria: year of publication, type, the department in which the thesis was conducted, research method, research design, study group/sample/review material, data collection instrument, data analysis method, and the AI application used. In this way, the current state, tendencies, and deficiencies of research on AI applications in Turkish language teaching have been systematically presented within the framework of the research criteria.

Method

This section presents information on the research design, study group/review materials, and the data collection and analysis procedures.

Research Design

This study was designed within the framework of a qualitative research approach, as it aims to comprehensively reveal trends in the literature on Turkish language teaching and artificial intelligence (AI) applications. Qualitative research refers to approaches that seek to explore the meanings individuals or groups attribute to social or human problems and to interpret these meanings in depth (Creswell, 2016).

Document analysis was employed as the data collection method. Document analysis involves the systematic collection, examination, evaluation, and interpretation of various documents and materials that serve as primary data sources for scientific research (Sak et al., 2021). The documents reviewed may include journals and similar written materials produced by society for the purposes of informing, entertaining, or guiding (Merriam, 2013). Accordingly, document analysis was preferred because it enables the systematic and in-depth examination of studies spanning a wide time range.

Review Materials

The materials examined within the scope of the study consist of a total of 30 works published between 2020 and 2025. Of these, 10 are theses published in the National Thesis Center of the Council of Higher Education of Türkiye (YÖK National Thesis Center), and 20 are articles indexed in Google Scholar and DergiPark. It was determined that the studies identified in accordance with the established criteria provided sufficient data diversity and representativeness to meet the purpose of the research.

The studies were included in the research based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria were as follows: the studies must address artificial intelligence and Turkish language teaching; must be full-text theses or articles published between 2020 and 2025; must be published in Turkish; and must include the keywords “Turkish education,” “Turkish language teaching,” “artificial intelligence,” “reading,” “writing,” “listening,” “speaking,” “generative artificial intelligence,” and “mother tongue.” These keywords were determined based on the most frequently used concepts in the literature. The exclusion criteria were as follows: studies published prior to 2020; studies published in languages other than Turkish; symposium or conference papers; studies without full-text access; and books or book chapters.

In selecting the studies, the thematic focus, purpose, and keyword alignment were prioritized rather than solely the academic departments of the researchers. In this context, studies produced in technical fields such as Natural Sciences or Computer Engineering—but focusing on Turkish language teaching processes (e.g., reading level assessment, text evaluation)—were also identified. In order to address the technological infrastructure of Turkish language teaching from an interdisciplinary perspective, studies that directly contribute to the teaching and assessment of language skills (Abed, 2021; Aksoğan, 2025) were also included.

Data Collection Process

The data were collected through document analysis in four stages. In the first stage, a comprehensive literature review was conducted to identify relevant studies, and a “review form” including the criteria and variables of the study was developed. This form was reviewed by two expert faculty members and finalized based on their feedback. The review form included criteria such as year, type, subject, study group, research method, research design, data collection instrument, data analysis method, and the AI application used in each study.

In the second stage, studies identified through searches of the YÖK National Thesis Center and relevant databases were evaluated according to the established criteria and subjected to a preliminary review in terms of document completeness. In the third stage, a second round of screening was conducted to enhance reliability, and the studies were re-examined and systematically classified according to the review form. In the final stage, unique codes were assigned to each study, and the data were transferred to a digital environment accordingly.

Data Analysis

Content analysis was used to analyze the data. In this process, the data were first coded; similar codes were grouped into categories, and these categories were then organized into themes.

The findings were tabulated and interpreted based on frequencies and distributions. Trends in the literature were identified according to variables such as year, type, subject, study group, research method, research design, data collection instrument, data analysis method, and the AI application used. Thus, the fundamental characteristics of the studies were described, and the overall landscape of the field was systematically presented.

Validity and Reliability

To ensure validity, the data collection and analysis processes were described in detail, ensuring transparency in the research procedure. In addition, expert opinions were sought during the development of the review form, and necessary revisions were made accordingly. To enhance reliability, the data were subjected to a two-stage screening process, the findings were periodically re-examined, and the classification process was conducted systematically.

Limitations

This study is limited to full-text Turkish theses and articles published between 2020 and 2025. The data collection process was restricted to the YÖK National Thesis Center, DergiPark, and Google Scholar databases; international databases such as Web of Science, Scopus, and ERIC, as well as books, book chapters, and conference proceedings, were excluded from the scope. This suggests that some important studies in the field may have been overlooked.

The fact that the study encompasses only Turkish-language publications excludes the findings and perspectives of research conducted in English and other languages. Therefore, it should be noted that the findings obtained are not sufficient for universal generalization.

The limitation of the number of studies examined to 30 makes it difficult to draw broad generalizations. In addition, since the content analysis process relies heavily on the researcher's interpretation, a certain risk of subjective judgment is inherent in the objective evaluation of the findings.

Furthermore, the exceptionally rapid pace of development in artificial intelligence tools limits the capacity of the studies examined to fully reflect current technological advancements. In this regard, the findings may partially lose their currency in the near future. Finally, it should be kept in mind that this study, being based on document analysis, is descriptive in nature and aims to systematically describe the existing literature rather than to establish causal relationships regarding the effects of artificial intelligence applications on Turkish language teaching.

Findings

This section presents the findings of a total of 30 studies (20 articles and 10 theses) on artificial intelligence applications and Turkish language teaching, examined within the scope of the research between 2020 and 2025. The data obtained through document analysis were analyzed using content analysis and systematically classified in line with the research problems. The findings obtained as a result of the analysis were categorized and presented under sub-headings according to the following variables: publication year, type, department in which the theses were conducted, research method, research design, study group/sample characteristics, data collection tools, data analysis methods, and the artificial intelligence application used. Visualized figures and frequency (*f*) values were used in the presentation of data.

Figure 1. Distribution of Studies by Year

Figure 1 presents the distribution of the studies examined within the scope of the research by year. An examination of the data in the figure reveals that there was one study ($f=1$) in each of the years 2020 and 2023, two studies ($f=2$) in 2021, and no studies in 2022. However, the increase in the number of studies to seven in 2024 indicates a growing academic interest in the topic. In 2025, 19 studies were added to the literature. The findings presented in Figure 1 demonstrate that the vast majority of the studies examined within the scope of the research were conducted in 2024-2025.

Figure 2. Distribution of Studies by Type

Figure 2 presents the distribution of the studies examined within the scope of the research by type. An examination of the data in the figure reveals that the studies were predominantly in the form of "articles." A total of 20 articles and 10 theses were identified.

Figure 3. Distribution of Theses by Department

Figure 3 presents the distribution of the thesis studies within the scope of the research by department. According to the figure, the vast majority of the theses ($f=6$) were conducted in the Department of Turkish and Social Sciences Education. One thesis ($f=1$) was conducted in each of the following departments: Primary Education, Advanced Technologies, Philosophy, and Computer Education and Instructional Technology.

Figure 4. Distribution of Studies by Research Method

Figure 4 shows that 17 of the studies were conducted using qualitative methods, eight using quantitative methods, and five using mixed methods.

Figure 5. Distribution of Studies by Research Design

Figure 5 presents the distribution of the studies examined within the scope of the research by research design. An examination of the data in the figure reveals that the most frequently used ($f=7$) research design was 'Literature Review / Systematic Review.' 'Case Study' and 'Survey Model' designs were each used in five ($f=5$) studies, while 'Phenomenology' was used in three ($f=3$) studies; 'Explanatory Sequential Mixed Design' ($f=2$), 'Experimental / Quasi-Experimental Designs' ($f=2$), and 'Document Analysis' ($f=2$) were each preferred in two studies. 'Design and Development Research,' 'Comparative Case Analysis,' 'Exploratory Sequential Mixed Design,' and 'Multi-Methodology' were each found in one ($f=1$) study.

Figure 6. Distribution of Studies by Study Group/Sample

Figure 6 shows the distribution of the studies examined within the scope of the research by study group/sample. An evaluation of the data in the figure reveals that the most frequently preferred study/sample group was 'Pre-service Teachers' ($f=7$) and 'Literature/Documents' ($f=7$). These two groups were followed by 'Teachers and Academics' ($f=6$) and 'Primary and Secondary School Students' ($f=5$). In addition, the number of studies that used 'AI Outputs' as a data source was 3 ($f=3$).

Figure 7. Distribution of Studies by Data Collection Tool

Figure 7 presents the data collection tools used in the studies examined within the scope of the research and their frequency. According to this figure, the most frequently used data collection tool was 'Document Analysis / Literature Review ($f=10$),' followed by 'Semi-Structured Interview Form ($f=9$).' 'Personal/Demographic Information Form ($f=6$)' was used in 6 studies, and 'Questionnaire Form ($f=4$)' in 4 studies. Among the data collection tools used in the studies, there were also measurement instruments specific to artificial intelligence. In this regard, the 'AI Literacy Scale' and the 'AI Anxiety Scale' were each used in two ($f=2$) studies. Additionally, the 'Observation Form' was selected as a tool in two studies. The remainder of the figure includes field-specific measurement tools used only once, showing diversity (audio recordings, checklists, etc.). Achievement tests, attitude scales, and evaluation forms developed and adapted for higher-order thinking skills and language skills were found to be used in individual studies. This situation indicates that, alongside the limited availability of standardized measurement tools in the field, different measurement tools specific to the nature of the topic studied were also used.

Figure 8. Distribution of Studies by Data Analysis Method

Figure 8 presents the distribution of data analysis methods used in the studies within the scope of the research. According to the data in the figure, researchers frequently used both quantitative and qualitative analysis methods. The most frequently preferred analysis methods were 'Descriptive Statistics (arithmetic mean, standard deviation, etc.)' and 'Content Analysis' ($f=10$). These were followed by 'Independent Samples t -test' ($f=9$), which reflects the predominance of difference tests in the analysis of quantitative studies. 'Descriptive Analysis,' preferred in the analysis of qualitative data, was found in seven studies, while 'One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA),' used for group comparisons, was used in five studies. 'Frequency and Percentage Analysis' and 'Document Analysis' were each found in four studies. Advanced statistical techniques and method-specific analyses were limited; 'Artificial Neural Networks / Deep Learning Models' and 'Paired Samples t -test' were each used three ($f=3$) times; 'ANCOVA (Analysis of Covariance)' and 'Correlation Analysis' were each used two ($f=2$) times; and 'Chi-Square Test' was used once.

Figure 9. Distribution of Artificial Intelligence Applications Used in the Studies

Figure 9 presents the distribution of artificial intelligence tools used or examined in the studies within the scope of the research. The most frequently encountered AI tool, with 18 uses, was ChatGPT (GPT-three and GPT-4), followed by the intelligent voice assistant Siri (Apple) and Google Assistant, each appearing in three studies. Canva (AI usage), Natural Language Processing (NLP), and Matlab each appeared twice. The remainder of the figure includes 'DALL-E, DeepL, Babbel, Alexa AI, Eduaide.AI, Rytr, Microsoft Designer, Speechify, ProctorEdu, Ai-proctor, as well as LISP, Deep Blue, Eliza, Kahoot, etc.,' each preferred in one ($f=1$) study.

Discussion

The chronological distribution of the studies reveals a significant increase in research on Turkish language teaching and artificial intelligence, particularly after 2023. While the number of studies conducted between 2020 and 2023 remained limited, a noticeable rise occurred from 2024 onwards, reaching its peak in 2025. This increase may be associated not only with the widespread accessibility of generative AI tools but also with the broader process of digital transformation in education. In particular, the rapid global adoption of ChatGPT and similar tools since late 2022 appears to have accelerated

academic interest in this field. The fact that ChatGPT is the most frequently used technology in the examined studies (Dal, 2024; Gün & Durmuş Öz, 2024; Sevinç & Yılmaz Özelçi, 2025) further supports this interpretation. In this context, it can be argued that research on artificial intelligence in Turkish language teaching is still in a developmental phase.

The findings also indicate that studies in this field are predominantly published in article format, while theses demonstrate an emerging interdisciplinary orientation. Although the topic has primarily been examined within the field of educational sciences, it has increasingly attracted attention from disciplines such as computer engineering and linguistics. For instance, Abed (2021) conducted a study in the Department of Advanced Technologies in which primary school students' reading levels were classified using voice processing technologies, demonstrating the applicability of AI in assessing reading skills. Similarly, Aksoğan (2025) developed deep learning models (Bi-LSTM) to evaluate Turkish text-based open-ended questions in a doctoral study conducted in the field of Computer Education and Instructional Technology. These examples illustrate that the field is shaped through the integration of pedagogical needs and technical solutions. This finding suggests that effective implementation of AI applications in Turkish language teaching requires interdisciplinary collaboration.

An analysis of the methodological tendencies reveals that qualitative research methods and literature review-based designs are predominantly employed in the existing studies. This indicates that the field is currently in an exploratory phase, where researchers prioritize understanding and describing the phenomenon before establishing causal relationships (Koparan & Şimşek, 2025). However, the limited number of quantitative and mixed-method studies that measure the direct effects of AI on language skills restricts the generalizability of the findings. Nevertheless, recent experimental studies have demonstrated that AI applications can create significant improvements in productive language skills such as speaking (Afşin, 2025) and writing (Dal, 2024), highlighting the need for greater methodological diversity in future research.

Analysis of the study groups and materials indicates that pre-service teachers and document-based materials are frequently preferred. The prominence of pre-service teachers as a study group may be attributed not only to accessibility but also to the intention of identifying the competencies required for future educators in the context of digital transformation. Existing studies indicate that pre-service teachers possess relatively high levels of AI literacy (Banaz & Demirel, 2024); however, they also express ethical and pedagogical concerns regarding the use of these technologies (Sarıkaya & Yıldız Şakiroğlu, 2025; Sevinç & Yılmaz Özelçi, 2025). On the other hand, the limited number of applied studies conducted with primary and secondary school students (Kır, 2025; Ürkmez, 2025) makes it difficult to observe how these technologies are reflected in real classroom practices. This situation is further supported by the predominance of qualitative data collection tools such as interviews and document analysis over experimental measurement tools and achievement tests.

From a pedagogical perspective, the findings suggest that artificial intelligence applications primarily function as supportive tools and idea generators in Turkish language teaching. These tools have been found to reduce students' writing anxiety and enhance creative thinking skills (Atasoy, 2025; Dal, 2024), while in speaking skills, they contribute to lowering anxiety by increasing self-efficacy perceptions (Afşin, 2025). However, in the context of reading skills, although AI applications appear to increase motivation, they do not consistently lead to significant improvements in reading comprehension (Ürkmez, 2025). This may be due to the complex and higher-order cognitive processes involved in reading comprehension, which require more than surface-level interaction with texts. Therefore, for AI applications to effectively support such cognitive skills, they need to be designed in alignment with instructional objectives and structured in a way that facilitates deeper cognitive engagement.

In addition, both teachers and academics tend to perceive AI as a tool that reduces workload (Yıldırım Bilgen & Karagöl, 2025). This transformation also leads to a redefinition of the teacher's role, shifting from a transmitter of knowledge to a guide and facilitator in the learning process (Aydoğdu, 2025; Kaya, 2023). This shift indicates that the integration of AI into education is not only a technological change but also a pedagogical transformation.

Conclusion

The success of this pedagogical and technological transformation within the educational system is undoubtedly directly related to the degree to which applications in different disciplines are scientifically grounded. In this context, quantitative and qualitative data are of paramount importance to observe the actual outcomes of AI-driven opportunities in educational settings and to sustain this transformation. Nevertheless, an overview of the current literature reveals that research addressing this need still suffers from certain methodological limitations.

Considering the predominance of descriptive and opinion-based studies in the literature, there is a clear need for more rigorous experimental and quasi-experimental research that can provide empirical evidence on the effects of AI applications on the four core language skills. Future studies should not be limited to text-based tools; instead, visual and auditory AI applications should also be integrated into Turkish language teaching processes, and their effectiveness should be comparatively examined.

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Ethics statement: In this study, we affirm compliance with the rules outlined in the "Higher Education Institutions Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Directive" and 1964 Declaration of Helsinki and its later amendments, and assert that none of the "Actions Against Scientific Research and Publication Ethics" have been undertaken. Furthermore, we declare that there is no conflict of interest among the authors, that all authors have contributed to the study, and that full responsibility for any ethical violations rests with the article authors.

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Data Availability Statement: The data (documents) analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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AI Use Declaration: During the preparation of this work, the authors used generative artificial intelligence (AI) tools solely for the purpose of English language translation and proofreading. The authors retain full responsibility for the accuracy, originality, academic integrity, and ethical compliance of all content included in the manuscript, regardless of this AI-assisted process.

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